

Classroom Teachers' 21st Century Skills in the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum Implementation: Basis for Policy Review to Increase NAT Scores

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Abstract

The shift from learners' content mastery to skill proficiency in the 21st century teaching-learning process have prompted the Department of Education (DepEd) to align teachers' skills and competencies. Despite the efforts, the results in the National Achievement Test (NAT) are comparably low. With this, the researchers conducted descriptive research which involved a survey to 663 elementary and high school teachers from the 14 divisions in DepEd Region X. These teachers were given with a validated questionnaire to measure their problem-solving skills, information literacy skills, and critical thinking skills as factors of 21st century teaching skills. Sociodemographic profiling of these teachers indicates that majority of them are aged 18-37 years old, female, have taken master's unit, more than six years in service, and have an individual performance commitment and review (IPCR) rating of very satisfactory. Findings reveal that the teachers' 21st century skills are in the average level with the three factors. These skills differ significantly with the teachers' educational level and IPCR rating. Moreover, the learners' 21st century skills have a mastery level descriptive equivalent of average across Grade 6, Grade 10 and Grade 12 levels based on the 2017-2018 NAT results. Through correlational analysis, it is ascertained that there is no significant association on the 21st century skills between teachers and learners. Given all these, a review on how learners acquire and develop 21st century skills is called for to ameliorate policy formulation in increasing NAT scores.

Keywords: 21st century teaching skills, learning achievement, K to 12 curriculum

I. Rationale

The term 21st century skills refer to a broad set of knowledge, skills, work habits, and character traits that are understood by educators, school reformers, college professors, employers, and others to be critically important to success in today's world, particularly in collegiate programs and contemporary careers and workplaces (Tugyan, 2016). The skills students needed by the time they completed schooling in previous generations, such as the ability to memorize facts, are no longer sufficient for the demands of the workforce and society in the 21st century. Skills such as critical thinking, collaboration, problem-solving, and social skills are recognized by employers and educators alike as important 21st-century skills (Child Trends, 2015).

The noticeable shift in educational goals toward equipping students with a broad range of skills is being recognized through education and curricular reform efforts. However, the shift in educational goals has not yet translated into practice, and countries are struggling with

how to fully implement the 21st century skills agenda that focuses on teaching and assessment that is aligned with the changing goals (Care, et al, 2018).

The transferal from content mastery to learners' proficiency in the 21st century skills have prompted DepEd to align teacher's skills and competencies. DepEd Order 35, series 2016, puts premium on the 21st century skills in the teaching and learning situation as a central feature of the K to 12 Basic Education Program. DepEd highlighted the following 21st century skills in the teaching and learning situation for the K to 12 basic education program delivery: (a) problem solving skills; (b) information literacy skills; and (c) critical thinking skills. Teachers are capacitated to enrich lessons with simple integration strategies emphasizing the 21st century skills that are developmentally appropriate.

In the recent National Achievement Test results, there is a continuous decline in the regional and national levels. Nelia V. Benito, director IV of the Bureau of Education Assessment, reported that majority of our learners are in low proficiency level in using the 21st century skills, i.e. problem solving, information literacy, and critical thinking skills, and that there were only few who achieved the proficient and highly proficient levels.

To understand this scenario, this study was conducted to establish the association of the teachers' 21st century skills and the learners' mastery level in the 21st century skills. This is seen to provide school administrators and teacher better perspective to improve their work engagement and target orientation in shifting our educational goals to 21st century skills.

II. Literature Review

The key to teaching creativity and innovation skills lies in creating quality learning environments that give learners the opportunity to solve authentic, real-world problems and to be inquisitive with an open mind. In such environments, learners are encouraged to utilize higher order thinking skills that involve thinking outside the square, analyzing, evaluating, elaborating, and creating. They are challenged to stretch their imagination so as to come up with new ideas using well-tested creative thinking strategies such as brainstorming, mind mapping, visual creativity, word association (Kivunja, 2014).

The shift concerns the recognition of the need for education systems to equip learners with competencies such as problem-solving, collaboration, critical thinking, and communication. The focus on these "21st century goals" is visible in education and curricular reform and has been promoted by a global discussion of changing work and societal needs (Care, et al, 2018).

Teachers needed tailored professional development to facilitate instruction that incorporates real-world relevance and critical thinking. The disconnect between the teacher and the administrator's perception of 21st-century education were also integral in exploring this school's approach to a 21st-century education. Although classroom observations showed that teachers are attempting some elements of 21st-century instruction, the study found that there is a weak articulation of the vision to the teachers (Lendis, 2014).

Smart social networking requires critical thinking and metacognitive skills and the ability to integrate and evaluate real-world scenarios and authentic learning skills for validation. Technology in the 21st century serves as an extraordinary tool to shape and enhance the learning environment. Digital literacy skills are necessary to ensure the technology is used to supplement and not substitute for high-quality instructional methods. Preservice teachers using digital technology with valuable skills are the most powerful tools in teaching in the 21st century (Boholano, 2017).

The 21st century systems of assessments must therefore be designed carefully to accomplish their desired purposes, while maximizing authenticity of tasks, validity of claims, and integration with curriculum, such that students, parents, teachers, schools, and policymakers can use the insights generated to improve learning (Bialik, et al, 2016).

However, results revealed that teachers are moderately competent in terms of 21st century skills. Teachers have assessed themselves as very satisfactory in the National Competency-Based Teacher Standard (NCBTS) rating. There is also a significant relationship between teachers' skills and job performance. Lastly, there is no significant difference on both when grouped according to profile. Therefore, the teachers' skills complement the NCBTS. It can be a very good tool to assess job performance for they are all anchored in the road map of the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA). The DepEd, with its programs, projects and initiatives go hand and hand with the NCBTS. It is recommended that DepEd should firmly implement the triangulation method of assessing job performance of teachers by means of intensive monitoring from the highest down to the lowest ranks other than just mere self-assessment (Pa-alisbo, 2017).

In the study on pre-service teachers, they are ready for using 21st century learner skills (cognitive skills, autonomous skills, collaboration and flexibility skills, innovativeness skills) and teacher skills (administrative skills, problem-solving skills, affirmative skills, flexible teaching skills, generative skills). However, it was also found that pre-service teachers were not able to make enough use of learner and teacher skills during their practicum teaching at schools. Moreover, a positive, medium, and significant correlation were found between 21st century learner skills and 21st-century teacher skills (Tican & Deniz, 2019).

Similarly, research findings mainly revealed that the Teaching English to Young Learners I-II (TEYL) course was found to be ineffective in preparing 21st century teachers. Pre-service teachers (PSTs) perspectives on the TEYL course and the reasons why it was found to be ineffective were presented under four themes respectively with the teacher qualifications stated in Partnership for 21st century skills: (1) the use of teacher qualifications to manage, integrate and construct new knowledge; (2) 21st century learning skills; (3) the use of technology and assessment; (4) reflection. Although few qualifications are thought to include in the course, still there are certain teacher qualifications to be improved in TEYL field from PSTs perspectives (Cakir & Gungor, 2017).

It is important to note that teachers play a big role in developing students 21st century skills. Results of structural equation modeling indicated that 21st century skills had a significant relationship with students' writing and speaking. The interrelationship among five sub-constructs of 21st century skills (critical thinking and problem solving, communication and collaboration, interpersonal skills, leadership, and technology literacy) were analyzed on speaking and writing scores. Among five sub-constructs of 21st century skills questionnaire communication and collaboration had the highest correlation with foreign language speaking score and technology literacy had the highest correlation with foreign language writing score (Motallebzadeh, et al, 2018). Also, a similar study indicates that the respondents acquired the different 21st-century characteristics of an educator to a large extent (Borja, 2018).

III. Research Methodology

A. Sampling

The respondents of this study are the 663 elementary, junior high school and senior high school teachers of the 14 divisions of DepEd Region X which were selected through

disproportionate stratified sampling. In this sampling procedure, the number of elements sampled from each stratum is not proportional to their representation in the total population. To compare strata to each other, enough elements were selected for each category. With this, the researchers' need to maximize the sample size of each stratum in which equal allocation is the most appropriate (Daniel, 2012).

B. Data Collection

A 23-item survey questionnaire on teachers' perception of 21st-century skills was administered. This tool was validated and tested for reliability ($\alpha=.96$). It utilized a Likert scale where 1 represents Strongly Agree to 4 which is Strongly Disagree.

The learners' NAT scores for SY 2017-2018 were primarily obtained from the Bureau of Education Assessment.

C. Ethical Issues

The principle on voluntary participation was employed in this research. An informed consent was explained thoroughly in terms of the procedures and nature of involvement to all the respondents in this study. To protect the privacy of the research participants, the research team guaranteed the confidentiality of their answers and remained anonymous throughout the study.

D. Data Analyses

Descriptive statistics were applied to understand the demographics of the sampled data and to analyze the teachers' perception of the 21st century skills and learners' NAT scores. The data gathered were encoded in MS Excel 2019.

Additionally, inferential statistics (ANOVA and Pearson Product Moment Correlation) set at .05 level of significance were used to probe on the teachers' perception of the 21st century skills and learners' NAT scores. Encoded data were migrated and processed using the IBM Statistical Package for Social Science Version 20.

IV. Results and Discussion

A. Respondents' Profile

Among the 663 teacher-respondents, 77 percent are females and 23 percent are males. For their generational bracket, 54 percent are millennials (18-37 y.o.), 38 percent are from the Generation X (38-53 y.o.) and 8 percent are baby boomers (54-65 y.o.).

Their educational background revealed that 79 percent of them have the mandatory bachelor's degree, only 18 percent have master's degree and 3 percent have doctorate degree.

Representing the learning areas, 19 percent of the respondents teach Filipino, 23 percent on Mathematics, 23 percent on English, 19 percent on Science, and 17 percent on Social Studies. Their length of service indicated that 9 percent taught less than a year, 36 percent taught 1-5 years, 20 percent taught 6-10 years, and 35 percent taught for more than 10 years.

In their recent individual performance and commitment review (IPCR), 30 percent of the respondents were rated outstanding by their immediate superiors, 65 percent were very satisfactory, and 5 percent have satisfactory rating.

B. Teachers' Perception on their 21st Century Skills

DepEd highlighted the following 21st century skills in the teaching and learning situation for the K to 12 basic education program delivery: (a) problem solving skills; (b) information literacy skills; and (c) critical thinking skills. The problem-solving skill allows learners to demonstrate skills in understanding the problem, analyzing outcome, and executing strategies or methods. Information literacy skill develops learners' competences in identifying types of information, managing information, and communicating information. And lastly in critical thinking skill, learners show ability in analyzing relevance, evaluating sources, and using evidence to formulate an argument. Table 1 shows the teacher-respondents' perception on the said 21st century skills.

Table 1. Teachers' perception on their 21st century skills.

	\bar{x}	SD	QD
Problem Solving Skills	1.83	.72	Average
Information Literacy Skills	1.88	.69	Average
Critical Thinking Skills	1.91	.68	Average
Weighted Mean	1.88	.68	Average

Legend:

- 1.00-1.49 High*
- 1.50-2.49 Average*
- 2.50-3.49 Low*
- 3.50-4.00 Very Low*

These teachers have average level skills in teaching their learners to identify the problem in each situation, present possible options to solve a problem, and select the best solution from the options. They also have average level skills in manifesting among their learners to recognize the need for timely information and identify potential sources of information. Moreover, they have average level skills in imbibing skills to their learners how to recognize similarities and differences among things or situations, search for evidence, facts, or knowledge by identifying relevant sources, and draw inferences or conclusions that are supported by evidence.

With series of capacity trainings that are conducted in DepEd for teachers to level up their classroom instruction in the K to 12 curriculum along with the strengthened monitoring and evaluation systems, these teachers must have practiced their know-hows on the teaching of the 21st century skills to the learners. It is placed with heavy emphasis among them that the current DepEd curriculum is learner centered.

The average level of the teachers' perception on their 21st century skills may be sufficient at this time, but it can still be improved to ideally reach the high level. This will need more resources, effort, and time for leaders to substantially equip all teachers in DepEd.

Furthermore, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to establish significant differences on the teachers' perception on their 21st century skills with their demographic profile. In Table 2, it is revealed that teachers' 21st century skills differ significantly with their educational attainment and IPCR rating only.

Table 2. Test of differences on the teachers' perception on their 21st century skills with their demographic profile.

	F	p
Gender	1.83	.18
Generational Bracket	.95	.42
Subject Taught	.74	.57
Length of Service	1.90	.13
Educational Attainment	6.89	.00**
IPCR Rating	3.81	.01**

*Level of significance is at .05.

**Level of significance is at .01.

From this information, it can be gathered that pursuing continuing education, either short-term training courses or graduate schooling, is beneficial for teachers to enhance their 21st century skills. It is with these continuing education initiatives that a teacher can be abreast with the up-to-date content and pedagogical knowledge that is supplemental for teachers to be a learner-centered teacher.

Also, it can be deduced that those teachers rated outstanding, very satisfactory or satisfactory are good reflectors of what a teacher is like inside the classroom in terms of manifesting the 21st century skills to their learners.

C. Learners' Mastery Level on the 21st Century Skills

It is in DepEd Order 55, series 2016, on the Policy Guidelines on the National Assessment of Student Learning for the K to 12 Basic Education Program, that exit assessments in Grades 6 and 10 will cover the 21st century skills using learning areas as content while the Grade 12 assessment will focus on the 21st century skills and the core senior high school learning areas. The test design is progressive in nature where the test items will measure varying skill levels of the learners.

Table 3 shows that the learners' mastery level on the 21st century skills based on the NAT 2017-2018 results are all in the average level. It can be safely assumed that these learners have fundamentally acquired the necessary competency for them to perform the 21st century skills. Albeit it is still far from the desired mastery level. This recognizes that there is still more room for these learners to hone these skills.

It can be gleaned also that the critical thinking skills of Grade 6 and 12 students are low. This skillset requires higher order thinking processes like analyzing, synthesizing and evaluating. It must be challenging for these learners to demonstrate these skills, thus, this can be taken as a perspective point where there is more work to be done to help these learners.

Looking at the subject areas covered in the NAT, it is on Filipino that our learners have comparably higher scores, while it is in the tool subjects – English, Science, and Mathematics – that our learners have the lowest scores in Grade 6 and Grade 10. English performance is better among Grade 12 students, but Science and Mathematics remain to be low.

Table 3. Learners' mastery level on the 21st century skills.

	Grade 6		Grade 10		Grade 12	
	\bar{x}	Mastery Level	\bar{x}	Mastery Level	\bar{x}	Mastery Level
Problem Solving Skills	37.77	Average	47.07	Average	35.87	Average
Information Literacy Skills	38.20	Average	46.12	Average	35.93	Average
Critical Thinking Skills	32.58	Low	41.81	Average	34.83	Low
Weighted Mean	36.18	Average	45.00	Average	35.54	Average

Legend:

0-4	<i>Absolutely No Mastery</i>
5-15	<i>Very Low</i>
16-34	<i>Low</i>
35-65	<i>Average</i>
66-85	<i>Moving Towards Mastery</i>
86-95	<i>Closely Approximating Mastery</i>
96-100	<i>Mastered</i>

This regional NAT results mirror the overall results in the national NAT scenario. According to then-Undersecretary for Curriculum and Instruction Lorna Dig Dino, the change in the design of the NAT whereby it specifically tested the 21st century skills as opposed to the previous assessment framework which was profoundly competency-based is seen as the contributory factor to the low mean percentage scores in the national level.

D. Teachers' and Learners' 21st Century Skills

It is very interesting to associate teachers' agency of the 21st century skills to their learners' development of the same 21st century skills. Through correlational analysis set at 95 percent alpha level, it is determined that there is no significant relationship between teachers' perception of their 21st century skills and the learners' mastery level of the said 21st century skills ($r=.15$, $p=.34$).

There could be more instrumental factors to the development of the learners' 21st century skills other than the teachers' intervention. Factors like (a) motivation and learning efficacy; (b) social and media exposure; and (c) socioeconomic sustenance could play in more substance and influence on the learners. Or statistically, one of these factors are potential mediating variable to establish the link between teachers' 21st century skills and the learners' 21st century skills.

The correlation results of this study might not agree to existing studies that stress on the association between the two given variables (Borja, 2018; Bialik, et al, 2016).

Contrariwise, there are literature that posits the non-linking of the teachers' and learners' equipment of the 21st century skills. Tican and Deniz (2019) argued that the relationship between 21st century learner skills and 21st century teacher skills is not strong.

Further, it was found that even pre-service teachers were not able to make enough use of 21st century learner and teacher skills during their practicum teaching at schools.

V. Conclusion

The movement in modern education in providing learners with 21st century skills is being vastly documented through education research and curricular reform efforts. DepEd followed suit so it stressed on the learner-centeredness in the K to 12 basic education curriculum.

Both 21st century skills of teachers and learners are of average level which could tolerably outlive the challenges present in this modern world. However, it is not enough and there is more effort to be done to improve their equipment of the skills.

The non-association between 21st century skills of teachers and learners is suggestive that the development of the learners' 21st century skills is a lifetime pursuit which could not only be factored in by their teachers in limited time and space. There are more various potential factors that could give in more bearing to the learner skills. It rather provides a holistic perspective in looking at the learner and the learning processes.

VI. Recommendations

1. Various factors like (a) the contextual delivery of the K to 12 curriculum of the teachers and (b) the learning styles of the learners can be looked into to better understand their 21st century skills formation.
2. Teachers' continuing education can be made more accessible for them to be abreast with teaching content and pedagogies.
3. Policy reviews on the curriculum, instruction and assessment can be done to come up with appropriate solutions to each subject area in every schools division.
4. Research qualitative techniques like field observation and structured discussions can be undertaken to have in-depth analyses of the study.

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